

Trioxomonofluovanadates (+5)

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Trioxomonofluovanadic acid, H_2VO_3F , or any of its salts has not yet been reported. Thermal analysis¹ of MF-MVO₃ system, where M = alkali metals, showed the formation of compounds having the formula MVO₃.2MF. But from a study of the ternary reciprocal system of the fluoride and metavanadates of sodium and potassium the formation of a compound having the composition KF.KVO₃ has been indicated².

The present authors have been able to isolate two compounds *viz.*, *o*-phenanthroline and α - α' -dipyridyl trioxomonofluovanadates respectively. The compounds have been studied through IR-spectra and thermogravimetry.

Both α - α' -dipyridyl and *o*-phenanthroline trioxomonofluovanadates were prepared by dropwise addition of aqueous solutions of corresponding base hydrochlorides to the aqueous solutions (ca. 6%) of either ammonium dioxotetrafluovanadate³, $(NH_4)_3VO_2F_4$ or potassium dioxotrifluovanadate⁴, $K_2VO_2F_3$, at room temperature with stirring. In both cases, yellow rhombic crystals immediately separated out from the solution. The crystals were filtered by suction, washed several times with acetone, dried in air and then over $CaCl_2$ and analysed. Found : N, 10.18; V, 18.95; F, 6.62%. $C_{10}H_8N_2.H_2VO_3F$ requires, N, 10.14; V, 18.45; F, 6.88%. Found : N, 9.59; V, 16.62; F, 6.40%; $C_{12}H_8N_2.H_2VO_3F$ requires, N, 9.33; V, 16.97; F, 6.33%.

It is interesting to note that these compounds were insoluble in water (both hot and cold) and also in common organic solvents *viz.*, in acetone, benzene, ethanol, chloroform, but readily soluble in hot glacial acetic acid.

Thermogravimetric study showed that the compounds remained stable upto 200° and after that decomposition started and continued upto 410° to the vanadic anhydride as the ultimate product. I.R. spectra, recorded in the region of 700–4000 cm^{-1} using KBr pellets, indicated the absence of water in these compounds. Exact vanadium-oxygen bands could not be ascertained from IR-spectrum, because both α - α' -dipyridyl and *o*-phenanthroline absorb in the same region⁵ (900–1000 cm^{-1}), at which vanadium-oxygen bond vibration takes place. However, strong absorption bands observed at 865 cm^{-1} , 935 cm^{-1}

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and 955 cm^{-1} for α - α' -dipy. $\text{H}_v\text{VO}_3\text{F}$ and at 850 cm^{-1} , 860 cm^{-1} , 935 cm^{-1} and 950 cm^{-1} for *o*-phenanthroline. $\text{H}_2\text{VO}_3\text{F}$, might be due to vanadium-oxygen stretching vibrations. Again absence of any broad intense band below 900 cm^{-1} (i.e., typical stretching vibrations⁶ of atoms in V-O-V-O-chains), in the above two compounds rules out the presence of V-O-V chains in these compounds.

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